

Packet Loss Aware Trust Management (PLATM) for IOT Network

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Abstract

In IoT applications security is an important criterion for sending information exchange. Packet loss is an important constraint in an IoT network which can be occurred because of numerous reasons like energy depletion, out of range communication due to mobility, low buffer capacity and congestion at buffer of node. Lack of such exploration the performance of any trust based security mechanism may affect that results an innocent node will suffers and the malicious nodes remain unexplored consequences in the network. To develop the trust model, this paper proposes a packet loss aware trust management (PLATM) for an IoT network. In this model the PLATM uses MAC layer information and residual energy status as an important evaluation metrics to measure the trust worthiness of node. Here the evaluation of trust worthiness is a composition of packet forwarding capacity and residual energy status of the node. Simulation analysis is implemented over the proposed approach and the performance metrics such as malicious detection rate, false positive rate and average packet loss ratio are measured. The obtained performance metrics results an eminent performance of proposed mechanism when compared with existing mechanism..

Keywords: IOT, packet loss, PLATM, IOT network

1. Introduction

In recent years, the rapid growth in the development of Internet of things (IoT) makes it to penetrate its widespread applicability into various fields including medical care, climate monitoring, industrial manufacturing and agricultural production [1]. Taking the advantage of IoT, different devices can be connected to the internet and they can communicate with each other and also can exchange information, which had given a great convenience in the daily lives. But as the number of devices connected to internet increases, the information exchange also increases which don't have any guarantee about the security [2]. Since the devices are connected to the internet, the information exchanged is at great risk of being stolen and modified. Due to the open environment and the flexible transmission medium, the IoT nodes may get compromised through various attacks like tampering, hijack, sinkhole, selective forwarding, DoS etc. To prevent the nodes getting compromised from these attacks, a Trust Management (TM) scheme needs to develop through which the every IoT node chooses a secure and trustworthy node before transmitting the information to it.

Towards this, a novel TM scheme is developed in this paper considering the communication scenario, and the energy status through the nodes. Mainly, this paper focused over two parameters; they are the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer information, and the residual energy status. A new probability factor is developed to decide the packet forwarding capabilities of a node based on its MAC layer and residual energy status. Simulation results conducted over the developed mechanism reveals the outstanding performance with respect to the performance metrics such as Malicious Detection Rate (MDR), False Positive Rate (FPR), and Average Packet Loss Rate (APLR).

Rest of the paper is organized as follows; Section II describes the details of state-of-art methods. Section III describes the details of Trust Management Scheme. Simulation results are illustrated in section IV and finally the conclusions are provided in section V.

2. State-of-art Methods and Problem Formulation

Various TM schemes are developed in earlier to ensure the trust based routing in IoT network. In the trust evaluation process, the parameters considered to define the trustworthiness of nodes. If these

parameters are more in number, then the node selected is said to be more trustworthy and also robust. Considering this multi parameter strategy, Chen et al. [3] proposed a new Trust and Reputation Model TRM-IoT based on Fuzzy Reputation and the parameters considered for trust evaluation are Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), energy consumption, and end-to-end packet forwarding ratio. However, this method didn't focus over the resource constraints. Focusing over only trust and reputation reduces the network lifetime. Further, a new method proposed by Bao and Chen [4] considered the community-interest, co-cooperativeness and honesty for trust evaluation. In the same year, a new strategy called, "Social Internet of Things (SIoT)" was proposed by Atzori et al. [5] in which the trust evaluation is done based on the social network aspects. Further, Nitti et al. [6] developed two trust models, Objective evaluation model and subjective evaluation model for trust management. Here the trust value of every node is measured based on the social behavior of a node towards its neighbor nodes. The trust is measured in an indirect way, i.e., the opinion of neighbor nodes decides the trustworthiness of every node. F. Gaiet. al., [7] proposed a new trust based anomaly detection technique based on multi-dimensional trust elements such as Reputation, Social Relationship, and Quality of Service (QoS). Based on these factors, the device is instructed to take a proper decision regarding the trustworthiness of a node. After that the trustworthiness is converted into trust levels based on fuzzy method, and the results will be used in the device's security policies to assess its peers.

Though these approaches focused over the secure provision but no method is there which was focused over the packet loss based misbehavior detection. All the methods have different strategies and the methods which considered packet loss as main base for misbehavior blindly declared the node as malicious if the packet loss is observed at any node. But this assumption can be wrong for some time because the packet may get lost due to many reasons. Towards this analysis, Shebaro et al., [8] proposed a fine grained analysis (FGA) scheme to analyze the packet loss reasons in Wireless sensor networks (WSNs). Three data related metrics namely; Received signal strength indicator (RSSI) [9], the link quality indicator (LQI) [10], and the Packet Reception Rate (PRR) are considered for analysis. This approach is much effective for WSN due to its static topology but is not suitable for IoT where there are heterogeneous nodes exist. P. Yulia and D. W. Seo [11] proposed a light weight and distributed method for the detection of various attacks against traffic flow based on the analysis of incoming traffic and fuzzy inference system. In the first phase, based on the PRR and packet Inter Arrival Time (IAT), a light weight thresholding mechanism is applied to select the traffic attributes. Recently, Sowmya G and Venkatram N [12] proposed a new trust ensuring mechanism with multi contextual aspects including the interactions between the IoT nodes and their energy levels. Furthermore, a minimum hop count mechanism is also proposed to select a path with less processing delay. Combining all these multi facets, a composite routing metric is derived in this paper to define the trustworthiness of IoT node before choosing it as a next hop communicating node. Though this approach retrieved an effective detection performance, it is not able to find the main underlying reasons for packet loss, resulted in the high FPR.

3. Proposed Mechanism

3.1. Overview

In this paper, a Packet Loss Aware Trust Management (PLATM) mechanism is proposed to find the malicious nodes in IoT network. Initially the proposed mechanism identifies the key parameters for analyzing the cause of packet loss under various aspects. The proposed PLATM uses MAC layer information, and Residual Energy Status as a main evaluation metrics to measure the trustworthiness of node. Each node locally analyzes the neighbor node's trustworthiness with respect to the Packet Forwarding Capability (PFC) using the proposed measures. Based on the obtained PFC, every node decides whether the neighbor node is trustworthy or not.

3.2. MAC Layer Information

MAC layer is one important layer at which there is a possibility to lose the packets due to several reasons. At MAC layer, the main reason due to which the packet loss may happen is congestion.

Congestion happens only when the link has limited bandwidth and the incoming data is of high data rate. Due to these constraints, congestion will occur resulting in a buffer overflow; an incoming packet may be dropped by the next hop node [14].

According to the standard IEEE 802.11 MAC layer specifications [13], after sending a data packet from sender node, it receives a Link Layer Acknowledgment (LLA) from the receiver node. This LLA is received within a predefined time interval and if not received, then the sender node assumes that packet may not receive at receiver node and packet is lost due to the malicious nature of receiver node. Hence the LLA signifies a trustworthiness of a node, if the sender receives the LLA within the time specified, simply it can assume that receiver node is trustworthy otherwise it is malicious. But this assumption may be wrong because, there are so many reasons, other than malicious nature for packet loss. There are some more reasons at MAC layer due to which the packet may get lost.

This paper considered the HELLO packets as probe packets and tries to detect the underlying cause for packet loss at MAC layer. In the IoT network, every node periodically exchanges the preset number of HELLO packets with its one-hop neighbor nodes [15]. Every node will receive only a fixed number of HELLO packets every time from its neighbors. If the node receives properly from all of its neighbor nodes, then it is assumed that all nodes are trustworthy. In this process, it is considered as no link problem and if any node drops the packet, then it can be noticed as malicious node. On the other hand, if a node does not receive the expected number of HELLO packets, then it can be assumed that some link interference problem is happened and if any packet is dropped, then it can be considered due to the internal problem only but not due to the malicious nature of neighbor node. In the data transmission phase, the forwarding node also shares the status of link information of its neighbor nodes. Based on this consideration, any node can evaluate the underlying main reason of packet loss. Consider two nodes A and B are communicating, let $P_{received}(t_{(i-1)}, t_i)$ be the total number of HELLO packet received in the time interval of $t_{(i-1)}$ to t_i , $P_{expected}(t_{(i-1)}, t_i)$ be the total number of expected packet to be received in the time interval of $t_{(i-1)}$ to t_i , the packet forwarding probability of node B can be measure at node A as,

Based on this trust metric, the node A can get clarity about the trustworthiness of node B and its forwarding capability. Generally the range of $P_F(A, B)$ is in $[0, 1]$, here 1 indicates that the node B is more trustworthy and it can forward data to further without any packet loss and 0 indicates that the node B is malicious and a increasing value for 0 to 1 indicates the increasing trustworthiness.

3.2. Residual Energy Status

At some instants, the source node assumes that the forwarding node has become malicious, if it is observed any packet loss. But this assumption is always not correct. Because, there may be a chance of less energy at forwarding node and packet may lost. Hence to preserve the energy resources, the node may become selfish and propagates a false message into the network. At that time, if a packet is lost at the forwarding node, then the source node may assume that the packet was lost due to the malicious nature of forwarding node. To solve such problem, this approach considered a metric called Residual Energy Status (RES) to determine the energy status at the neighbor nodes. Every neighbor node periodically communicates it to the source node as a part of HELLO packets. The Probability of successful packet forwarding with respect to the energy factor is formulated as;

$$P_F(A, B) = P_{received}(t_{i-1}, t_i) / P_{expected}(t_{i-1}, t_i) \quad (1)$$

Where E_P is the initial energy of a node P, $((E_R)/E_P)$ is the RES, and E_R is the residual energy remained after forwarding the packet and it is obtained as

$$P_E = (E_R / E_P) \quad (2)$$

Where E_{P^Q} is the energy consumed due to the transmission of packet of node Q. As the residual energy increases, the probability of packet forwarding also increases and vice versa. It is important to note that the forwarding node may send a false HELLO packets regarding its residual energy. To get correct information about the residual energy, the source node not only considers the direct RES value but also considers the indirect RES value which is obtained from the common neighbor nodes.

3.4. Composite Metric

Based on the above analyses regarding the two different packet forwarding probabilities, a composite metrics is proposed here by combining P_M and P_E . The composite metric derived here is named as Composite Packet Forwarding Metric (CPFM). For a given two communicating nodes, A and B, the CPFM can be formulated as,

$$CPFM(A,B) = \alpha * P_M + \beta * P_E, \text{ s.t } \alpha + \beta = 1 \quad (4)$$

Where α and β are the two random weights assigned to two different probabilities. These weights are completely application and network dependent and there is no fixed values. The value of CPFM is evaluated by sender node and compared with correct behavior of its neighbor nodes, in order to measure the correctness of evaluated trustworthiness by the underlying trust based scheme.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section describes the details of simulation experiments performed over the proposed PLATM and the obtained performance results including the Average Packet Loss Ratio (APLR), Malicious Detection rate (MDR), and False Positive Rate (FPR) are stipulated here. The performance evaluation is accomplished by varying the total number of malicious nodes. To simulate the proposed framework, an IoT network with N number of nodes is created with an area of $M \times N$, where M is the length and N is the width of the network. The simulation parameters are listed in Table.2.

Table.1 Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of nodes	30-100
Area	1000*1000 m ²
Mac	IEEE 802.11
% Malicious behavior	0-50% of total nodes
Traffic Source	Constant Bit Rate
Node placement	Random
Trust threshold	0.6
α, β	$0 \leq \alpha, \beta \leq 1$

Figure.1 MDR for varying (a) % of malicious nodes and (b) Data Rate (packets/sec)

Figure.2 FPR for varying (a) % of malicious nodes and (b) Data Rate (packets/sec)

Figure.3 APLR for varying (a) % of malicious nodes and (b) Data Rate (packets/sec)

4.1. Performance analysis of PLATM

In this set of simulation experiments, we evaluate the proposed PLATM in terms of MDR, FPR and APLR for varying number of malicious nodes and data rate (Packets/sec).

MDR: MDR is measured as a ratio of total number of IoT nodes detected as malicious to the total number of original nodes. Fig.1 describes the details of MDR evaluation for varying total number of nodes and data rate. Since the proposed approach mainly focused over the packet loss, the simulation is accomplished by varying the data rate and the obtained MDR is depicted in fig 1(b) as the number of nodes increases the malicious node count also increases and in such case the effectiveness of proposed detection mechanism is elevated with high MDR. As it can be seen from fig 1(a) for every instant of percentage of malicious nodes, the PLATM as obtained higher MDR compared to conventional MCTAR-IoT[12]. Furthermore, as the data rate increases the number of packets arrived at every forwarding node increases. If the forwarding node don't have sufficient buffer capacity then simply it drops and the source node may assume the forwarding nodes has become malicious. This assumption leads to an increased FPR and reduced MDR as it can be seen from fig 1(b) even though the MDR follows decreasing characteristics, for every instant of data rate the proper PLATM has higher MDR compare to conventional one.

FPR: FPR is measured as a ratio of total number of nodes detected as malicious when they are nonmalicious. The main focus of PLATM is reduce the FPR since there are so many cases like MAC layer, residual energy through which the packet may get lost and the source node may assume the forwarding nodes as malicious which increases FPR. During the trust evaluation if these parameters are also included the FPR with varying percentage of malicious nodes and data rate is represented in figure 2(a) and 2(b) respectively. In both cases the proposed PLATM has obtained a less FPR value than conventional MCTAR-IoT since the MCTAR – IoT was not focused on packet loss oriented analysis for malicious node detection, the FPR is slightly high compare to the proposed PLATM.

APLR:APLR is measured as a ratio of total number of packets lost by total number of packets sent. The total number of packets is measured by subtracting total number of packets delivered minus total number of packets transmitted. As the number of malicious nodes increases packet loss also increases as depicted in figure 3(a). Similarly the APLR follows a linear relationship with datarate. As shown in figure 3(b) the proposed approach due to the consideration of MAC layer and energy status for packet loss evaluation.

9. Footnotes

Use footnotes sparingly (or not at all) and place them at the bottom of the column of In IoT network, the packets may get loss due to several reasons like energy depletion, lower buffer capacity, link interference etc. The trust management scheme assumes every loss of packet due to the malicious nature of intermediate nodes those are helping to forward the information form source node to destination node. But, this assumption consequences to a wrong analysis about the nodes. This problem is solved by considering the packet loss as a main factor in the trust evaluation process and this paper proposed PLATM by considering the packet loss at MAC layer and also the packet loss due to energy depletion. A composite routing metric is derived by combining these two parameters and at every phase, the node checks the trust status of next hop node by comparing with a trust threshold. Extensive simulations are conducted over the proposed PLATM and the obtained results shown an outstanding performance compared to the state-of-art methods.

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